

PROBLEM SOLVING METHODS IN ANALYTIC GEOMETRY**Ibroximov Baxtiyor Toyirjon o'g'li****Ma'rufjonov Rejabboy Valijon o'g'li****Gulomov Saidakbar Oybek o'g'li***Andijan State University,**Faculty of Physics and Mathematics**Teacher*

Annotation : It is known that mutual perpendicular which was horizontal and vertical numbers read Descartes right angular coordinates system formed does . This system through in the plane point with a couple in the middle of a real number a valuable compatibility is set. This in our work geometry simple issues in solving some methods listed

The key word : Geometry , figure , axiom , point , coordinate , plane .

INTRODUCTION

The science of geometry has an ancient history, the basic concepts of which originated in Egypt and Babylon 4,000 years ago. The emergence of geometric knowledge is related to the practical activities of people. This is reflected in the names of many geometric figures. For example , a trapezoid name Greek trapezion - from the word obtained and the " table . " indicates _ The term " line " Latin limem - « flax from the word " thread " yield which was .

From ancient times geometry axioms to the system basically Created firm logical fanga become _ He is uninterrupted evolving new theorems , ideas and methods with rich went _

From our era in the earlier III century Greek scientist Euclid called "The Foundations ." asarini writes . Euclid this period which was geometric knowledge summed up and it is the completion of science axiomatic statement to give movement did . From Euclid then lived scientists to his " Fundamentals. " some topics added , clarifications entered .

Of geometry current time physics with link observation very interesting . Mostly math enriched new concepts physics and chemistry and of natural sciences other sections is coming . For example , vector from mechanics obtained example can be. Of geometry next in development esa of mathematics internal demand and to himself specific logical development as a result his in to the body new _ _ geometric concepts new modern physics to create the way opened . For example , Lobachevskiy geometry relativity theory to open basis become service did .

Current time geometry very much a lot links has _ From them one geometry numbers theory with , the latter quantum physics with , the third esa mathematician analysis with brings it closer . Current time mathematics sections such that then geometry more , algebra or to say analysis _ _ difficult _

METHOD AND RECOMMENDATION

In the plain point $A(x, y)$ with determined . x, y to numbers his coordinates is called . The phrase " , given a point " means that its coordinates are given, and the phrase "Find the point N " means to find these coordinates. Coordinates system through installed such compatibility **coordinates method** is called .

This method geometry **simple issues to solve** we use

1) In the plain given $A(x_1, y_1)$ and $B(x_2, y_2)$ points between distance find Demand let it be . It is known $AC = x_2 - x_1$ that $BC = y_2 - y_1$, ABC right angular triangle ,, $AB^2 = (x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2$ so _ so that

$$AB = \sqrt{(x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2} \tag{1}$$

will be . (1) to the formula in the plane given two point between distance find formula is called (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Figure 2 Figure 3

2) Given the AV cross section, let its ends $A(x_1, y_1)$ and $B(x_2, y_2)$. AB let the problem of finding the point that divides the section be proportional $AC : BC = \lambda$. $C(x, y)$ It is known from high school geometry (Figure 2),

$$AC : A_1C_1 = BC : B_1C_1 = \lambda,$$

or

$$\frac{AC}{BC} = \frac{A_1C_1}{B_1C_1} = \lambda$$

as _

$$A_1C_1 = x - x_1, B_1C_1 = x_2 - x$$

that is for ,

$$(x - x_1) : (x_2 - x) = \lambda, \quad x - x_1 = \lambda(x_2 - x); \quad x + \lambda x = x_1 + \lambda x_2;$$

$$x = \frac{x_1 + \lambda x_2}{1 + \lambda}$$

will be . Similarly , _

$$y = \frac{y_1 + \lambda y_2}{1 + \lambda}.$$

So, C of the point coordinates for

$$x = \frac{x_1 + \lambda x_2}{1 + \lambda}, y = \frac{y_1 + \lambda y_2}{1 + \lambda} \quad (2)$$

formulas yield we did. (2) formula AB cut λ in proportion divisor $C(x, y)$ point find formula is called. Private without $C(x; y)$ point AV cut teng to two if so, it is ahead

$$\frac{AC}{CB} = \lambda = 1 \text{ as } , x = \frac{x_1 + x_2}{2} - y = \frac{y_1 + y_2}{2}$$

cut teng to two to be formula come turns out.

3) That's right angular coordinates in the system tips $A(x_1; y_1), B(x_2; y_2), C(x_3; y_3)$ at points which was triangle face The following formula is arched can be found :

$$S = \frac{1}{2} [(x_1 y_2 - x_2 y_1) + (x_2 y_3 - x_3 y_2) + (x_3 y_1 - x_1 y_3)] \quad (3)$$

1-m *isol* . $M(5; 3)$ and $N(2; -1)$ points between find the distance .

Solution . Condition according to $\therefore x_1 = 5, y_1 = 3, x_2 = 2, y_2 = -1$ These are given by formula (1) read :

$$MN = \sqrt{(2 - 5)^2 + (-1 - 3)^2} = \sqrt{9 + 16} = \sqrt{25} = 5$$

It will be.

2 -**example** . In the plain $A(5; 3), B(2; 1)$ points given . AV cut $\frac{AC}{CB} = \lambda = 0,2$ in proportion divisor $C(x; y)$ of the point find the coordinates .

Solution . Condition according to $x_1 = 5, x_2 = 2, y_1 = 3, y_2 = 1, \lambda = 0,2$. (2) formula basically :

$$x = \frac{x_1 + \lambda x_2}{1 + \lambda} = \frac{5 + 0,2 \cdot 2}{1 + 0,2} = \frac{5 + 0,4}{1,2} = \frac{5,4}{1,2} = \frac{54}{12} = \frac{27}{6} = \frac{9}{2} = 4,5;$$

$$y = \frac{y_1 + \lambda y_2}{1 + \lambda} = \frac{3 + 0,2 \cdot 1}{1 + 0,2} = \frac{3 + 0,2}{1,2} = \frac{3,2}{1,2} = \frac{32}{12} = \frac{16}{6} = \frac{8}{3}.$$

That's right will $C\left(4,5; \frac{8}{3}\right)$ flow . _

3-m **isol**. Tips $A(2; 0)$, $B(5; 3)$ and $C(2; 6)$ at points which was of the triangle find his face .

Solution . (3) to the formula according to $x_1 = 2$, $x_2 = 5$, $x_3 = 2$, $y_1 = 0$, $y_2 = 3$, $y_3 = 6$ that is for ,

$$S = \frac{1}{2}[(2 \cdot 3 - 5 \cdot 0) + (5 \cdot 6 - 3 \cdot 2) + (0 \cdot 2 - 2 \cdot 6)] = \frac{1}{2}(6 + 24 - 12) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot 18 = 9$$

It will be.

Example 4 $A(-6;7)$ and $B(-2;3)$ points given . AB cut C, D, E points through 4 equal components separated _ C, D, E division find the points (Figure 3).

$$\text{Solution : It is known } \frac{AC}{CB} = \frac{1}{3}, \frac{AD}{DB} = 1. - \frac{AE}{EB} = 3$$

C of the point coordinates from formula (2) using we find :

$$x_c = \frac{-6 + \frac{1}{3}(-2)}{1 + \frac{1}{3}} = -5, y_c = \frac{-6 + \frac{1}{3} \cdot 3}{1 + \frac{1}{3}} = 6$$

So ,. _ $C(-5, 6)$ (D and E points find to the reader link is provided).

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